

THREE-DIMENSIONAL THERMOELASTICITY FORMULATION FOR LAMINATED TRANSVERSELY ISOTROPIC SOLIDS

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ABSTRACT

A thermoelastic problem defined by a set of four coupled partial differential equations with appropriate boundary, interface, and initial conditions is formulated. The three components of the generalized equation of motion are coupled to the transient linear heat conduction equation by accounting for thermal stresses. The material considered is a laminate consisting of two transversely isotropic layers. The top surface is subjected to a point heat flux, which is a step function in time. Both the top and bottom surfaces are cooled convectively. The solution is decomposed into steady-state and transient parts. The proposed numerical solution proceeds by performing a Fourier integral transformation in a plane parallel to the interlayer interface and a Chebyshev collocation process in the remaining direction. The steady-state solution is obtained by solving a set of linear equations, and the transient by separating time and depth variables and solving the resulting quadratic matrix eigenvalue problem.

INTRODUCTION

The solution of the coupled thermoelastic equations in composite laminates has gained interest in recent years due to a large body of research in the field generally categorized as nondestructive evaluation. Özisik¹ discusses heat conduction in isotropic laminates and in single-layer anisotropic solids. Beavers² and Hand³ analyze heat conduction in a laminate consisting of two individually anisotropic layers. Several problems in thermoelasticity are presented by Nowinski⁴ and Nowacki.⁵ However, relatively little work has been done on coupled thermoelastic problems in composite laminates. Iravani and Nikoonahad⁶ present the appropriate thermoelastic governing equations in anisotropic media, but solve only the heat conduction equation.

A three-dimensional coupled thermoelastic formulation for laminated transversely isotropic layers of the same material is presented here. The solution procedure is described in detail, including algorithm implementation. A laminate consisting of two transversely isotropic layers subjected to a steady point heat flux at a surface is considered. The procedure can be adapted to more practical cases consisting of infinite-layered composites subjected to temporally and spatially varying heat fluxes.

FORMULATION

The structural coordinate system used in the governing equations is depicted in Fig. 1. For each layer, the composite material properties are given with respect to the individual material coordinate system. The material properties are then transformed to a structural coordinate system (Fig. 1).⁷

The coupled thermoelastic partial differential equations are expressed in Cartesian index notation. Following Nowinski,⁴ the thermoelastic equations are written as

$$c_{ijkl} \left[\frac{1}{2} (u_{k,lj} + u_{l,kj}) \right] + \rho b_i + \beta_{ij} \theta_{,j} - \rho \ddot{u}_i = 0 \quad (1a)$$

$$(k_{ij} \theta_{,j})_{,i} - c_\epsilon \rho \dot{\theta} + \rho g + T_0 \beta_{ij} \dot{u}_{i,j} = 0 \quad (1b)$$

The three components of the equation of motion are given by (1a), and the transient linear heat conduction equation by (1b). Material properties within a single layer are assumed constant over the temperature range considered.

The thermal moduli and thermal expansivities are related by

$$\beta_{ij} = -c_{ijk\ell} \alpha_{k\ell} \quad (2)$$

Fig. 1. Structural coordinate system.

If internal heat generation and body forces are neglected, combination of (2) and (1a,b) yields

$$c_{ijk\ell} \left[\frac{1}{2} (u_{k,\ell j} + u_{\ell,kj}) - \alpha_{k\ell} \theta_{,j} \right] - \rho \ddot{u}_i = 0, \quad (k_{ij} \theta_{,j})_{,i} - c_e \rho \dot{\theta} - T_0 c_{ijk\ell} \alpha_{k\ell} \dot{u}_{i,j} = 0 \quad (3a,b)$$

The boundary and interface conditions are zero traction stresses at the top and bottom layers of the laminate and continuous traction stresses and displacements at the interface. The thermal boundary conditions consist of energy balances on the top and bottom laminate surfaces. The heat flux is applied to the top surface (Fig. 1). Both surfaces are cooled by convection. Radiative heat transfer is neglected. The heat flux and temperature are continuous across the interface.

The unknowns are the temperature and three components of displacement within each layer. The elastic boundary and interface conditions involving traction stresses must, therefore, be expanded in terms of the unknown displacements. The traction stresses are written in terms of displacements using

$$\sigma_{ij} = c_{ijk\ell} \left[\frac{1}{2} (u_{k,\ell} + u_{\ell,k}) - \alpha_{k\ell} \theta \right] \quad (4)$$

The equations of motion and heat conduction (3a,b) are rewritten in dimensionless form as

$$\mu_{ijk\ell} \left[\frac{1}{2} (u_{k,\ell j} + u_{\ell,kj}) - E \gamma_{k\ell} \theta_{,j} \right] - \ddot{u}_i = 0, \quad (\omega_{ij} \theta_{,j})_{,i} - H \dot{\theta} - H \mu_{ijk\ell} \gamma_{k\ell} \dot{u}_{i,j} = 0 \quad (5a,b)$$

where the dimensionless spatial coordinates and time carry a layer subscript because they depend on the individual layer thicknesses.

The dimensionless elastic boundary and interface conditions are:

Top ($z_A = -1$)

$$s_{xzA}(x_A, y_A, -1, \tau_A) = 0, \quad s_{yzA}(x_A, y_A, -1, \tau_A) = 0, \quad s_{zzA}(x_A, y_A, -1, \tau_A) = 0 \quad (5c-e)$$

Interface ($z_A = 1, z_B = -1$)

$$s_{xzA}(x_A, y_A, 1, \tau_A) = c_r s_{xzB}(x_B, y_B, -1, \tau_B) \quad (5f)$$

$$s_{yzA}(x_A, y_A, 1, \tau_A) = c_r s_{yzB}(x_B, y_B, -1, \tau_B) \quad (5g)$$

$$s_{zzA}(x_A, y_A, 1, \tau_A) = c_r s_{zzB}(x_B, y_B, -1, \tau_B) \quad (5h)$$

$$u_{xA}(x_A, y_A, 1, \tau_A) = d_r u_{xB}(x_B, y_B, -1, \tau_B) \quad (5i)$$

$$u_{yA}(x_A, y_A, 1, \tau_A) = d_r u_{yB}(x_B, y_B, -1, \tau_B) \quad (5j)$$

$$u_{zA}(x_A, y_A, 1, \tau_A) = d_r u_{zB}(x_B, y_B, -1, \tau_B) \quad (5k)$$

Bottom ($z_B = 1$)

$$s_{xzB}(x_B, y_B, 1, \tau_B) = 0, \quad s_{yzB}(x_B, y_B, 1, \tau_B) = 0, \quad s_{zzB}(x_B, y_B, 1, \tau_B) = 0 \quad (5l-n)$$

The dimensionless thermal boundary and interface conditions are

Top ($z_A = 1$)

$$\begin{aligned}
 & -\omega_{xzA} \frac{\partial \theta_A(x_A, y_A, -1, \tau_A)}{\partial x_A} - \omega_{yZA} \frac{\partial \theta_A(x_A, y_A, -1, \tau_A)}{\partial y_A} - \omega_{zzA} \frac{\partial \theta_A(x_A, y_A, -1, \tau_A)}{\partial z_A} \\
 & + Bi_A \theta_A(x_A, y_A, -1, \tau_A) = \Omega(x_A, y_A, -1, \tau_A)
 \end{aligned} \quad (5o)$$

Interface ($z_A = 1, z_B = 1$)

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \omega_{xzA} \frac{\partial \theta_A(x_A, y_A, -1, \tau_A)}{\partial x} + \omega_{yZA} \frac{\partial \theta_A(x_A, y_A, 1, \tau_A)}{\partial y_A} + \omega_{zzA} \frac{\partial \theta_A(x_A, y_A, 1, \tau_A)}{\partial z_A} \\
 & = \omega_{xzB} \frac{\partial \theta_B(x_B, y_B, -1, \tau_B)}{\partial x_B} + \omega_{yZB} \frac{\partial \theta_B(x_B, y_B, -1, \tau_B)}{\partial y_B} + \omega_{zzB} \frac{\partial \theta_B(x_B, y_B, -1, \tau_B)}{\partial z_B}
 \end{aligned} \quad (5p)$$

$$\theta_A(x_A, y_A, 1, \tau_A) = \frac{k_{11r}}{L} \theta_B(x_B, y_B, -1, \tau_B) \quad (5q)$$

Bottom ($z_B = 1$)

$$\begin{aligned}
 & -\omega_{xzB} \frac{\partial \theta_B(x_B, y_B, 1, \tau_B)}{\partial x_B} - \omega_{yZB} \frac{\partial \theta_B(x_B, y_B, 1, \tau_B)}{\partial y_B} \\
 & - \omega_{zzB} \frac{\partial \theta_B(x_B, y_B, 1, \tau_B)}{\partial z_B} - Bi_B \theta_B(x_B, y_B, 1, \tau_B) = 0
 \end{aligned} \quad (5r)$$

The initial conditions are

$$\theta_A(x_A, y_A, z_A, 0) = 0, \quad \theta_B(x_B, y_B, z_B, 0) = 0 \quad (5s,t)$$

$$u_{xA}(x_A, y_A, z_A, 0) = 0, \quad u_{xB}(x_B, y_B, z_B, 0) = 0 \quad (5u,v)$$

$$u_{yA}(x_A, y_A, z_A, 0) = 0, \quad u_{yB}(x_B, y_B, z_B, 0) = 0 \quad (5w,x)$$

$$u_{zA}(x_A, y_A, z_A, 0) = 0, \quad u_{zB}(x_B, y_B, z_B, 0) = 0 \quad (5y,z)$$

The relationship between dimensionless stress and displacement in each layer is given by

$$s_{ij} = \mu_{ijk} [\pi_1 (u_{k,l} + u_{l,k}) - \gamma_{kl} \pi_2 \theta] \quad (6)$$

PROPOSED SOLUTION PROCEDURE

The first step in the solution is to perform a Fourier integral transformation on (5a-z) in the x - and y -directions. The unknown variables (u_x, u_y, u_z , and θ) are then functions of assigned dimensionless wavenumbers (ϕ_x and ϕ_y), the dimensionless depth dimension (z), and dimensionless time (τ). The transformed equations are then decomposed into transient and steady-state components. For example, the temperature field within the top layer is given by

$$\bar{\theta}_A(\phi_{xA}, \phi_{yA}, z_A, \tau_A) = \left[\bar{\theta}_A(\phi_{xA}, \phi_{yA}, z_A, \tau_A) \right]_t + \left[\bar{\theta}_A(\phi_{xA}, \phi_{yA}, z_A) \right]_{ss} \quad (7)$$

The subscripts "t" and "ss" denote, respectively, the transient and steady-state solutions, and "=" denotes a Fourier-transformed variable. The temperature difference in the bottom layer and the displacement components in each layer are similarly decomposed into steady-state and transient parts.

1. Transient Solution

The transient solution satisfies Fourier-transformed versions of the thermoelastic equations, homogeneous boundary conditions, and nonhomogeneous initial conditions. The transient system is, therefore, identical to (5a-z), with the following exceptions: (a) the heat source on the top surface, Ω , is zero; and (b) all initial conditions are set to the negative of the corresponding steady-state solution. For example, the transient temperature in the top layer satisfies the initial condition

$$\left[\bar{\theta}_A(\phi_{xA}, \phi_{yA}, z_A, 0) \right]_t = - \left[\bar{\theta}_A(\phi_{xA}, \phi_{yA}, z_A) \right]_{ss} \quad (8)$$

The transient system becomes a differential eigenvalue problem when z and τ are separated by a substitution of the form

$$\left[\bar{u}_x(z, \tau) \right]_t = \sum_{i=1}^N C_{ai} U_{xi}(z) e^{\lambda_i \tau} \quad (9)$$

for each layer. Each eigenvalue λ_i is the same for all layers. The eigenfunctions (U_x, U_y, U_z, θ) must be determined in each layer. The constants $C_a, C_b, C_c,$ and C_d (associated with each variable) are determined in each layer when the initial conditions are applied (*vide infra*).

Substitution of (9) into (5a,b) yields the quadratic differential eigenvalue problem

$$[L_2 \lambda^2 + L_1 \lambda + L_0] \underline{V} = \underline{0}, \quad (10)$$

where $L_2, L_1,$ and L_0 are 4×4 matrices consisting of zero elements or linear differential operators in z , the latter having elements of the form

$$L_k(i, j) = C_{k2}(i, j) \frac{d^2}{dz^2} + C_{k1}(i, j) \frac{d}{dz} + C_{k0}(i, j), \quad (11)$$

\underline{V} is a vector of eigenfunctions, $\underline{0}$ is a null vector-valued function, and $C_{k2}(i, j), C_{k1}(i, j),$ and $C_{k0}(i, j)$ are constants depending on material properties and wavenumbers.

When (9) is substituted into the transient boundary conditions, the time dependence cancels out because the boundary conditions are homogeneous and independent of τ . The top and bottom layer boundary conditions are expressed as

$$BC_A \underline{V}_A = \underline{0}, \quad BC_B \underline{V}_B = \underline{0}, \quad (12)$$

where \underline{V}_A and \underline{V}_B are vectors of eigenfunctions for layers A and B, respectively, and BC is a matrix, the elements of which consist of linear differential operators.

When (9) is substituted into the interface conditions, the $e^{\lambda_i \tau}$ term again cancels out because the interface conditions are homogeneous and independent of time. The elastic and thermal conditions at the interface are written as

$$IF \underline{V}_{AB} = \underline{0}, \quad (13)$$

where \underline{V}_{AB} is an 8×1 vector,

$$\underline{V}_{AB} = [\underline{V}_A \mid \underline{V}_B]^T, \quad (14)$$

and IF is an 8×8 matrix of differential operators at the interface.

The eigenfunctions in (10, 12-13) are expanded in terms of a complete set of functions. The following series of Chebyshev polynomials is substituted for the functions in the vector \underline{V}

$$U_{xi}(z_j) = \sum_{m=1}^N A_{mi} T_m(z_j) , \quad (15)$$

where $T_m(z_j)$ is the m -th Chebyshev polynomial evaluated at the j -th z -location, and A_{mi} , B_{mi} , C_{mi} , and D_{mi} are the m -th Chebyshev coefficients evaluated for the i -th eigenvalue. Each series contains N Chebyshev polynomials and coefficients. Substitution of (15) into (10) gives

$$[L'_2 \lambda^2 + L'_1 \lambda + L'_0] V' = 0 , \quad (16)$$

where

$$\underline{V}' = [\underline{A}_m \mid \underline{B}_m \mid \underline{C}_m \mid \underline{D}_m]^T \quad (17)$$

contains only Chebyshev coefficients and has length $4N$. The matrices L'_2 , L'_1 , and L'_0 contain Chebyshev polynomials and their z -derivatives. The order of L'_2 , L'_1 , and L'_0 is $4 \times 4N$.

The same procedure is followed when Chebyshev polynomials are substituted for the vector \underline{V}' in (12) and (13), the matrix representations of the boundary and interface conditions, giving

$$BC'_A \underline{V}'_A = 0 , \quad BC'_B \underline{V}'_B = 0 , \quad IF' \underline{V}'_{AB} = 0 . \quad (18)$$

A collocation process is used to transform L'_2 , L'_1 , and L'_0 from matrices containing Chebyshev polynomials to constant matrices. To properly choose the z -values within each layer, the number of equations and unknowns must be equal. After the interior collocation points are chosen, L'_2 , L'_1 , and L'_0 can be evaluated at each interior point, yielding

$$[L''_2 \lambda^2 + L''_1 \lambda + L''_0] V'' = 0 , \quad (19)$$

where L''_2 , L''_1 , and L''_0 are constant matrices of order $4M \times 4N$, and M is the number of interior collocation points in each layer. Once the double-primed coefficient matrices are calculated, they are combined into the quadratic matrix eigenvalue problem

$$[L''_{2AB} \lambda^2 + L''_{1AB} \lambda + L''_{0AB}] V''_{AB} = 0 , \quad (20)$$

where \underline{V}''_{AB} is the combined Chebyshev coefficient eigenvector of length $8N$.

The quadratic matrix eigenvalue problem (20) is singular and is reduced to a nonsingular problem in which the eigenvalue appears linearly, using the procedure described by Pearlstein and Goussis.⁸

The application of the initial conditions [e.g., (8)] completes the transient solution procedure. The constants [e.g., C_{ai} in (9)] are evaluated using initial conditions. After the eigenfunctions and the steady-state solution are known, the application of initial conditions at the collocation points results in a linear equation system which can be solved.

2. Steady-State Solution

The steady-state solution satisfies (5a,b) with the time derivatives set to zero. The boundary conditions are (5c-r). Using the collocation and Chebyshev polynomial substitution process described in §1, the steady-state problem is reduced to a linear equation system

$$L''_{0AB} \underline{V}''_{AB} = \underline{S} , \quad (21)$$

where L''_{0AB} and \underline{V}''_{AB} are the same as in (20), the vector \underline{S} is defined by

$$\underline{S} = [0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 1 \mid \underline{0}_1]^T , \quad (22)$$

and $\underline{0}_1$ is a zero vector of length $8N-4$. The unit component in \underline{S} corresponds to the Fourier-transformed heat source in the top thermal boundary condition.

3. Total Solutions

The total solution of each unknown function is the linear superposition of the transient and steady-state components, which is a function of the wavenumbers ϕ_x and ϕ_y . Therefore, the solutions are calculated for an appropriate number of wavenumber pairs. The inverse Fourier-transform is applied to return the solution to the x-y plane. The total solutions are then dimensionalized.

REFERENCES

1. Özisik MN, Heat Conduction, Wiley-Interscience (1980).
2. Beavers FL, Master's Rept., Univ. Arizona, Tucson (1986).
3. Hand DQ, Master's Thesis, Univ. Arizona, Tucson (1988).
4. Nowinski JL, Theory of Thermoelasticity with Applications, Sijthoff and Noordhoff International Publishers (1978).
5. Nowacki W, Thermoelasticity, PWN-Polish Scientific Publishers (1986).
6. Iravani MV and Nikoonahad M, J Appl Phys, 62 (1987), 4065.
7. Vinson JR and Sierakowski RL, The Behavior of Structures Composed of Composite Materials, Martinus Nijhoff Publishers (1986).
8. Pearlstein AJ and Goussis DA, J Comp Phys, 78 (1988), 305.

NOMENCLATURE

c_{tr}	Trace of stiffness tensor
α_{tr}	Trace of thermal expansivity tensor
k_{ij}	Thermal diffusivity = $k_{ij}/\rho c_e$
x_A	Dimensionless x-direction in top layer = $2x/L_A$
y_A	Dimensionless y-direction in top layer = $2y/L_A$
z_A	Dimensionless z-direction in top layer = $-1 + 2z/L_A$
θ	Dimensionless temperature difference = $(2k_{11}/q_0 L)\theta$
τ	Dimensionless time = $(2\sqrt{c_{tr}/\rho}/L) t$
u_i	Dimensionless displacement in i^{th} direction = $(4c_{tr}\alpha_{tr}\kappa_{11}T_0/L^2q_0)u_i$
μ_{ijkl}	Dimensionless stiffness tensor = c_{ijkl}/c_{tr}
γ_{ij}	Dimensionless thermal expansivity tensor = α_{ij}/α_{tr}
ω_{ij}	Dimensionless thermal conductivity tensor = k_{ij}/k_{11}
s_{ij}	Dimensionless stress tensor = σ_{ij}/c_{tr}
Ω	Dimensionless applied heat flux at top surface = q/q_0
E	Dimensionless constant in equation of motion = $c_{tr}\alpha_{tr}^2T_0/\rho c_e$
H	Dimensionless constant in heat conduction equation = $L\sqrt{c_{tr}/\rho}/2k_{11}$
Bi	Biot number = $h_{fc}L/2k_{11}$
c_r	Dimensionless stress ratio = c_{trB}/c_{trA}
d_r	Dimensionless displacement ratio = $(L_B/L_A)^2 c_{trA}\alpha_{trA}\kappa_{11A}/c_{trB}\alpha_{trB}\kappa_{11B}$
L_r	Layer thickness ratio L_A/L_B
k_{11r}	Fiber-direction thermal conductivity ratio = k_{11A}/k_{11B}
π_1	Coefficient in dimensionless stress expansion = $Lq_0/(4c_{tr}\alpha_{tr}\kappa_{11}T_0)$
π_2	Coefficient in dimensionless stress expansion = $Lq_0\alpha_{tr}/2k_{11}$